

Challenges of Pronunciation to EFL Learners in Spoken English

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 04 , 2024</p> <p>Accepted: July 07, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Challenges, Pronunciation, Segmental Features, Suprasegmental Features, Mother Tongue, Interference.</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12681039</p>	<p><i>This study is an attempt to investigate the challenges that encounter EFL learners in proper and correct pronunciation in spoken English. Moreover, the study aims at casting the light on the significance of pronunciation in teaching as well as learning to any educational institution which adopts English as a course in the curriculum, particularly at the tertiary level. The researchers have followed the analytical methodology via exploiting the questionnaire for data collection. The data presentation, analysis via Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS), and discussion, supported with tables and graphs are all included in the paper to reach appropriate findings and recommendations that could possibly contribute to the language learning problem-solving research attempts. Thus, studying the causes of pronunciation issues to EFL learners is an extremely significant matter emerges from the need to communicate properly with the entire world. Correction of pronunciation mistakes made by EFL learners is almost a daily matter that both researchers are dealing with on a regular basis, so it has been mutually decided to investigate the roots of the problem in order to find helpful appropriate solutions.</i></p>

Introduction

Teaching pronunciation to EFL learners has been ignored and avoided immensely due to various reasons. One reason is that non-native EFL teachers are not competent enough to teach pronunciation rules to learners. Another reason is that the vast majority of non-native teachers are not fluent enough in English because they either haven't studied English in an English-speaking country or not been exposed enough to an English-speaking environment. A third factor is that the teaching process of pronunciation itself is kind of hectic since it requires utilization of audio-visual devices which makes a very massive number of teachers refrain from teaching it. A fourth factor is that teachers do not use authentic materials to teach pronunciation which hence makes it just like any other theoretical course rather than being practical and interactive. A fifth cause is that most teachers do not adopt active learning strategies in their classes rather they tend to use a teacher-centered approach of teaching which makes learners bored to death in those classes. Undoubtedly teaching pronunciation properly is extremely significant and surpasses the boundaries of teaching speaking skills for the sake of communication.

1. Definition of Pronunciation

Mazouzi cited in (Roach, 2002: 61): Many people think that when talking about pronunciation in language learning we mean the way certain sounds are produced while speaking. But this is not helpful to say that pronunciation is an act of producing sounds of language. Many scholars have defined pronunciation from different perspectives. For Seidlhofer (2001: 56) pronunciation is "...the production and perception of the significant sounds of a particular language in order to achieve meaning in contexts of language use". Moreover, generally the meaning of a sentence will be understood from the way it is pronounced (Harmer, 2001: 184). It means that when learners speak in intelligible manner they will understand and convey the desired meaning. And, for learners to be intelligible they must understand what is heard and to be understood by using simple language tools to convey the messages.

Pronunciation also plays a great role in our lives, in a way that we project our identity through our way of speaking, and also shows our membership of particular communities (Seidlhofer, 2001: 56). All of this may be the reason why teachers think of teaching pronunciation as an important and difficult field.

2. Overview of English Pronunciation

Correct pronunciation brings success to EFL students anywhere in the world. In contrast, inadequate proficiency of English pronunciation impacts the progress of communicative aptitude that is required for building up the communicative bridge between speakers and listeners.

(Lin 2014) cited in (Gilakjani, 2011; Jahan, 2011): Precisely speaking, great pronunciation competence in English is able to make others understand easily; however, English pronunciation lesser to basic level augments the misinterpretation among conversations with others. It is not essential to speak English like a

native speaker but “acceptably to be understood” (Jesry, 2005). Obviously, the favorable impact of good pronunciation in the process of learning English is certain and strengthened; thus, ESL students should be taught standardized ways of English articulation (Gilakjani, 2011).

(Lin 2014) cited in (Charity, & Mallinson, 2011): Talking of the standardized English articulation, the fact that students’ language dissimilarities influence how they perform in academic years of schools should not be neglected. Especially, phonological discrepancy is one of language variables involving learning processes (Sinha, Banerjee, Sinha, & Shastri, 2009). Rather, sound patterns of learners’ first language are likely to affect their pronunciation in target languages (Jahan, 2011; as cited in Jesry, 2005; Zhang, 2009). Understandably, non-standardized English-speaking students are therefore afraid of being teased or feel embarrassed when they try to pronounce English accurately (Nogita, 2010).

It is obvious that differences in phonological system of mother languages will hinder rather than promote English pronunciation learning (Huang & Radant, 2009). To improve EFL students’ English pronunciation, teachers thus should obtain perceptions into their pronunciation variations, which will provide teachers with ideas of designing various teaching strategies for dealing with those students’ challenges in learning English pronunciation. In fact, teachers are able to help all students learn standardized English without diminishing their linguistic backgrounds through knowing their language variations (Charity & Mallinson, 2011). Accordingly, verbal assessment should not be based on specific norms, but take linguistic differences into account and value students’ voices. It goes without saying that knowing English language variation of ESL students will ultimately assist teachers prepare to instruct their students, perceive the learning challenges, and help students solve the problems (Dalle & Young, 2003). Hazen stated that “if people had a better understanding of how language works, they would probably be less inclined to make negative judgments about speakers of different dialects” (Hazen, 2001, p. 1). Undeniably, “language is integral to both culture and identity, an understanding of language variation and language diversity is critical to multicultural education” (Charity & Mallinson, 2011). “We can’t teach what we don’t know” (as cited in Charity & Mallinson, 2011). Therefore, understanding pronunciation variations facing ESL students can help teachers be aware of students’ dialect diversity and challenges in learning standardized English articulation.

With a central idea on the interference of first language, the above discussions present the significance of being able to speak English with good articulation as well as the difficulties and problems EFL learners encounter while acquiring English pronunciation. Unquestionably, the brief theoretical overview discussed above is essential in order for readers to understand the answer of the inquiry question addressed in this article. The next section will discuss the answer of the inquiry question through reviewing relevant literature with regard to major pronunciation challenges encountering EFL learners today.

3. Significance of Teaching Pronunciation

Mazouzi cited in (Murphy, 2003: 116): Some teachers have the idea that learners will learn to pronounce English well with little or no direct instruction. Others give extensive attention to aspects of pronunciation teaching. For Celce-Murcia (1996) pronunciation plays a crucial role in language teaching and learning. It is non-negligible even if the necessity and importance to teach it has been debated and changed a lot. Learning a language usually includes the aim of being able to communicate, and having good pronunciation is an effective factor for good communication. What pronunciation is responsible for is intelligibility between the speakers. Pronunciation is taught in isolation, but this doesn’t mean it should be regarded as separate areas of language learning. It can be regarded as contributory strands in the fabric of English (Broughton et al., 1980: 64). What pronunciation is responsible for is intelligibility between the speakers i.e. the aim of teaching pronunciation is not to achieve a total set of native speaker-like variations but to ensure intelligibility, by enabling the students to produce the English speech which is intelligible in the area where they will use it (Broughton et al., 1980: 58).

Mazouzi cited in (Bailey, 2003: 50): Moreover, we should make our speech understood by others, in order to communicate effectively in a target language. The inaccurate use of suprasegmental elements or mispronounce of phonemes will cause problems; for instance, it will be extremely difficult for speaker from another language community to understand (Kelly, 2000: 11). Nevertheless, “a learner who is aware that their pronunciation is quite good may grow in confidence and then perform better in other aspects of speaking, such as maintaining fluency” (Watkins, 2005:50).

4. Segmental and Supra-segmental Features of Pronunciation

As claimed by Burns. A and Claire. S (2003:4):

Pronunciation can be something of a ‘Cinderella’ in language teaching - to be given low priority or even avoided. Some teachers indicated that they were unsure about all the various features of pronunciation. Some were also unclear about whether to teach it separately or as an overall part of teaching activities.

Studying English as a foreign language can be a challenging effort for learners whose goal is to communicate effectively. One reason for the learners’ difficulty is the sound system of English. The area of

English pronunciation that is worth focusing on is of two aspects; segmental and suprasegmental which are separate entities combine and interact to explore the role played by the speaker and the listener. They are important in helping language users to master the spoken language through intensive exposure to those aspects. Segmental aspects are related to those features of the language which are recognized as separated segments, such as vowels and consonants of a particular language and how they make up a syllable that can be uttered. Suprasegmental, is the features that related to properties extending over the range of a single segment or the range of vowels and consonants which includes intonation patterns and stress placement, rhythm, and sounds that extend over syllables, words, and phrases. According to Brown, A (2014) cited in (Laver 1994,p152)that supra-segmental as “factors which can potentially be prolonged beyond the domain of the segment’, such as pitch, rhythm, intonation, stress.”

5.1. Segmental vs. Supra-segmental

As segmental and suprasegmental phonology of English language represent fairly complex areas of study; they should be explored very superficially by taking a brief look at the two phenomena of single phoneme, word, stress and intonation. Investigating features concerning individual sounds or phonemes detail, requires working on the segmental level since each phoneme is usually assumed to be one segment of speech. On the other hand, looking at larger chunks of speech, such as whole words or phrases, we deal with features on the suprasegmental level. The various features of English pronunciation are illustrated in the following figure:

Figure (1): Features of English Pronunciation(Burns, A and Claire. S. 2003:20).

5. Factors that Impact Learning English Pronunciation

Many studies in the field of (S/FLA) discussed the factors that impede achieving native-like pronunciation among foreign languages learners in general and among Arab learners specifically(O'Connor, 2003; Yule, 2003). Researchers and linguists have pointed some factors such as the differences of the sound system between the first language (L1) and the second language (L2), the inconsistency of some sounds in English language, the mother tongue interference and the influence of spelling on pronunciation. These factors were discussed separately as follows:

6.1. Mother Tongue Interference

Several works have been conducted on the influence of L1 in learning English language.(Wilkins 1972.p.199) observes that when learning a foreign language, a personis already familiar with his/her mother tongue, and it is this which s/he tries to transfer. The transfer may prove to be acceptable because the construction of the two languages is similar - in that case we get ‘positive transfer’ or ‘facilitation’- or it may prove baseless because the structure of the two languages isdissimilar in that case we get ‘negative transfer’- or interference.

Second language learners appear to accumulate structural entities of the target language but demonstrate difficulty in organizing this knowledge into appropriate, coherent structures. When speaking the target language, learners tend to rely on their native language (L1) structures to produce a response. If the structures of the two languages are distinctly different, then one could expect a relatively high frequency of errors to occur in L2, thus

indicating an interference of L1 on L2. Dulay et al (1982.p 25) defines interference as *“the automatic transfer, due to habit, of the surface structure of the first language onto the surface of the target language.”*

6.2. Little Amount of Exposure to the Target Language

According to language learning theories such as Krashen's (1982), learners acquire language mainly from the input they receive and they require large amounts of 'comprehensible input' before being expected to speak. On this basis, exposure to the (TL) would be a critical factor in pronunciation acquisition. However, Revell, P (2012 p.9) states that:

Nowadays, this claim is more likely to be modified to include 'proficient', rather than 'native-speakers of the F/SL, including the non-native class teacher. It could also include 'comprehensible input' via a variety of multimedia channels such as TV, radio, DVD or synchronous on-line chat rather than simply face-to-face conversation.

According to Ancker (2000:21), errors can occur for some reasons, for instance, interference from the first language; incomplete knowledge of the target language and the complexity of the target language itself. Kenworthy (1988:4-9) stated that: *“Factors such as the native language, the age, amount of exposure, phonetic ability, attitude and identity, motivation and concern for good pronunciation have great influence on pronunciation learning”.*

6.3. Sound System Differences between LI and L2

As it has been mentioned by many linguists and researchers, there is a conflict between the sound systems of LI and L2. These studies have shown that the main problem in teaching and learning English pronunciation result from the differences in the sound system of English and the native language. In Arabic, each letter represents only one sound, so it's easy to read any word from a written text. Also, there is no sound which is not pronounced (silent), as it happens a lot in English. When there is a difference in the sound system in the LI and L2 showed that errors are expected to be committed because the learners transfer their mother tongue sound system into the target language.

In English language there are twenty-four consonants and twenty vowels; that mean there are forty-four phonemes in English language the learner should be able to produce them while learning English. *“Learners of different language backgrounds will of course face some difficulties to pronounce them because of their language background”* (O'Connor, 2003.p 22). In Arabic language the whole number of the sounds is less than the one in English language, so the total sounds of Arabic language are twenty-eight letters each of them represents only one sound. So, there are only twenty-eight sounds in Arabic language.

6.4. Inconsistency of English Vowels

One of the important problems faced by the students of English is that, each English vowel has more than one pronunciation. So, this causes many difficulties to the learners and leads them to a mispronunciation. Instead of using the exact quality and quantity of a special sound, the learner erroneously changes either the quality or the quantity of the sound; so, in a certain word the learner tends to use the variant sounds e.g. son /sʌn/, come /kʌm/, among /əməŋ/, blood /blʌd/; in all these words /o/ and /oo/ stand for the same sound of /ʌ /, but most of the learners, unless they have a mastery of the pronunciation of such vowels, they mispronounce those words.

The learner, who doesn't have sufficient knowledge of different pronunciations of the vowels above, meets some difficulty, since s/he uses different variants of their pronunciations.

(Kharma and Hajjaj 2011.p.14) summarized this as: The spelling of Arabic is overwhelmingly regular. In contrast, the spelling of English is seemingly very irregular. Moreover, to the learner, written English is not always a reliable guide to pronunciation, and they are often misled by the graphic representation of sounds. (Swan and Smith's 2002: 196) have stated that *“English has 22 vowels and diphthongs to 24 consonants”*, while *“Arabic has only six vowels and no diphthongs ... to 32 consonants.”*

6.5. Influence of Spelling on Pronunciation

Even when students are equipped with both abilities to hear sounds in sequence and grasp English rhythm, there remains the fact that English spelling is so complicated that it is hard even for native speakers to learn. Speakers of many other languages in which the sounds and the letters are more closely connected have a much easier time learning to spell in their L1 than native speakers of English have learning to spell in theirs. Both phonetics and phonology deal with sounds. As claimed by (Forel, C. A., & Puskás, G. 2005.p.3) that:

English spelling and English pronunciation are two very different things. For instance, English has not 5 or 6 but 20 different vowels, even if these vowels are all written by different combinations of 6 different letters, "a, e, i, o, u, y". e.g. please, [pli:z]. Thus, the word please consists of three consonants, [p, l, z], and one vowel, [i:].

(O'Connor, 2003) claimed that some words which are ordinarily spelt in the same way are different in their pronunciation. Also, there are some words spelt in a different way, but have the same sound e.g., rain, rein, reign, all of them are pronounced /rein/. The learner, who still doesn't have the mastery of pronunciation of such words, pronounces each of them by looking at its spelling, and he is expected to mispronounce them. So, if the

learner doesn't know such relationship between sound and spelling, s/he mispronounces words by just looking at their spellings e.g., before the n the k is silent; knee, know, knot, knight a student who didn't learn their pronunciation correctly, pronounces them with the /k/ sound. Any time the student meets such words he will be confused to pronounce them correctly he just guesses the pronunciation by looking at the spelling of the word unless he has previous background.

6.6. Lacking of Motivation

Motivation has been broadly accepted by both teachers and researchers as one of the vital factors that affect the rate and success of second/foreign language (L2) learning. Motivation provides the principal incentive to initiate learning the L2 and later the driving force to sustain the long and often tedious learning process; indeed, all the other factors involved in L2 acquisition presuppose motivation to some extent.

According to Zoltan Dornyei (2009, 217): *“Without sufficient motivation, even individuals with the most remarkable abilities cannot accomplish long-term goals, and neither are appropriate curricula and good teaching enough on their own to ensure student achievement.”* On the other hand, high motivation can make up for considerable deficiencies both in one's language aptitude and learning conditions.

Although 'motivation' is a term frequently used in both educational and research contexts, it is rather surprising how little agreement there is in the literature with regard to the exact meaning of this concept? As has claimed by Zoltan Dornyei (2009, 217): *“Researchers seem to agree that motivation is responsible for determining human behavior by energizing it and giving it direction, but the great variety of accounts put forward in the literature of how this happens may surprise even the seasoned researcher.”*

6. Study Questions

This study is an attempt to investigate the challenges that encounter EFL learners in proper and correct pronunciation in spoken English. Moreover, the study aims at casting the light on the significance of pronunciation in teaching as well as learning to any educational institution which adopts English as a course in the curriculum, particularly at the tertiary level.

In order to achieve the above aims, the paper is designed to seek answer to the following questions:

1. What are the most common pronunciation challenges that EFL learners encounter in English language when they speak? However, sub-questions has been stated as follow:

- 1.1 To what extent factors such as mother-tongue interference and little amount of exposure to the target language contribute to pronunciation weaknesses?
- 1.2 What are the plans and techniques that considered the most effective in encouraging learners to improve their pronunciation?

Moreover, this paper is trying to investigate the roots of the problem in order to find helpful appropriate solutions.

8. Methodology and Study Population

Researchers have adopted the analytical research methodology by means of using SPSS program for data analysis of a questionnaire that has been distributed to a random sample group of 100 tertiary level students.

The age of the students (males and females) ranges between (18-22) years old. They study English as their specialization and as a foreign language in a formal setting. They have a similar language history or background in the sense that they all had spent 7 years learning English before joining college. None of them had been to an English- speaking country. All of them are native speakers of Arabic Language.

1. English language learners encounter pronunciation problems due to lack of practice.

Since 70 % of the responders strongly agreed to the statement, 20 % agreed, and 10 % were neutral, this proves that “English language learners encounter pronunciation problems due to lack of practice” is valid.

Chart (1) elucidates that lack of pronunciation practice causes problems.

2. English language learners confuse between similar sounds in pronunciation such as /p/ and /b/, /f/ and /v/, etc.

Since 66 % of the participants strongly agreed to the statement, 24 % agreed, and 10 % were neutral, this proves that “English language learners confuse between similar sounds in pronunciation such as /p/ and /b/, /f/ and /v/, etc.” is valid.

Chart (2) shows that learners confuse between similar sounds.

3. Silent letters cause a major problem in pronunciation.

In this statement 58 % of the responders strongly agreed, 34 % agreed, and 8 % were neutral, which proves that “Silent letters cause a major problem in pronunciation” is valid.

Chart (3) clarifies that silent letters cause a major problem in pronunciation.

4. Diagraphs are considered problematic to English learners in pronunciation.

According to the responses in statement: “Diagraphs are considered problematic to English learners in pronunciation” 30 % of the participants strongly agreed, 20 % agreed, 14 % neutral, 16 % disagreed, and 20 % strongly disagreed, which proves that the statement is acceptable.

Chart (4) displays that diagraphs are considered problematic to English learners in pronunciation.

5. Some English sounds do not exist in learners' languagephonological system.

According to the responses in relation to the statement: “Some English sounds do not exist in learners' language phonological system.” 36 % of the participants strongly agreed, 42 % agreed, 6 % disagreed, and 16 % were not sure, which proves that the statement is valid.

Chart (5) demonstrates that some English sounds do not exist in learners' language phonological system.

6. Stress position in isolated words is different for student to apply.

Chart (6) reflects that all respondents 100% decided that they failed in placing stress on the correct syllable. Hence, word stress placement is one of the main pronunciation difficulties.

Chart (6) shows that stress position in isolated words is different for student to apply.

7. Syllabication is the most problematic area for learners.

As shown in chart (7), 98% of the subjects, strongly agreed or agreed that they faced difficulties with words syllable division. This was an indication that learners were aware of their weaknesses regarding pronunciation elements. Only 2% were not sure.

Chart (7) demonstrates that syllabication is the most problematic area for learners.

8. Vowel length is difficult for learners to distinct.

Chart (8) provides an answer that 100% of the study subjects had difficulty in the vowel length contrast such as /æ/ and /ɑ:/. This means that vowel length differentiation is considered as a major problematic area.

Chart (8) clarifies that vowel length is difficult for learners to distinct.

9. Learners have challenges with consonantal clusters.

Chart (9) shows the responses on consonantal clusters difficulties such as “*spring*” and “*next*”, 90% of learners faced problem with consonant clusters. The respondents who strongly disagreed or disagreed were represented by the low percentage 10%. What is learnt from this distribution is that the pronunciation of consonants cluster seemed to be a major problematic area.

Chart (9) shows that learners have challenges with consonantal clusters.

10. Intonation rules are difficult for learners to use properly.

According to chart (10), the results revealed that applying intonation rules is considered as obstacles face students. 90% of the participants strongly agreed or agreed that the; %6 disagreed. The remaining was not sure. Hence intonation is one of the common difficulties of EFL pronunciation.

Chart (10) explains that intonation rules are difficult for learners to use properly.

9. Findings

The study has reached several different findings based on the segmental and suprasegmental analysis of the collected data:

- A. Students make mistakes in pronouncing some consonant sounds like (/p/ and /v/) mixing them up with (/b/ and /f/).
- B. Students mispronounce the consonant sound /r/ as Arabic /r/ sound which is pronounced as a velarized alveolar flap, i.e., with rolling the tongue.
- C. Students confuse the pronunciation of the letter (c) when it is /s/ or /k/.
- D. Students mispronounce diagraphs such as (sh, ch, ph, th, gh, wr, kn).
- E. Students mix up long and short monothongs.
- F. Students make an intralingual error of mispronouncing the vowel sound /ɜ:/ confusing it with the sound /ɔ:/ in words like: (word, worm, worship, work, etc.). Also, they do not pronounce this sound correctly in words like: (first, thirsty, burst, burn, etc.).
- G. Students do not pronounce diphthongs properly.
- H. Students misplace stress at both the word and the sentence level.
- I. Students do not use intonation correctly to differentiate between statements and questions.

10. Discussion

11. Recommendations

Researchers recommend the following:

- A. Teaching pronunciation requires highly trained teachers who are truly capable of correct pronunciation themselves. In other words, teachers should be really fluent with a solid background knowledge about pronunciation.
- B. Utilization of audio-visual authentic materials is highly recommended in teaching pronunciation classes.
- C. Student-centered approach of teaching is greatly advised to be adopted in teaching pronunciation. Students should be actively and practically engaged in the learning process since they are the targeted people meant to learn.
- D. A knowledge of learners' mother tongue is advised in order to enable teachers to understand the similarities as well as the differences between the source and the target language.
- E. Pronunciation teachers should be allowed to teach other related courses so they can be able to follow up students' progress.

12. Conclusion

A language is inarguably a tool of communication but it's definitely the persons' decision to make his/her tool in the best condition possible or not. Today no doubt that people need to use English almost all over the world to achieve a number of purposes such as business, studying, tourism, research, technology, jobs, etc. Thus, correct pronunciation is essential since mispronunciation of some words could possibly lead to serious misunderstandings. Having a native-like fluency would certainly be a plus in one's language skills credit and it can get a person through situations like job interviews, delivering oral presentations, and even daily conversations by making a good impression to people making them comfortable talking to you rather than selective in their language use to find something that suits your language standard.

Teaching pronunciation should be dealt with more carefully and with precise consideration as it's crucially important matter. Raising the awareness of both teachers and learners to the significance of correct pronunciation is a fundamental thing to be done. Investigating the challenges of correct pronunciation that students encounter requires further studies, research, and workshops if not conferences. Teachers are extremely advised to check the pronunciation of words before teaching them to learners because it will be fossilized into their brains.

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